

МІСЦЕВЕ ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ EMDOGAIN FL У ПАЦІЄНТІВ ІЗ ЗАХВОРЮВАННЯМИ ТКАНИН ПАРОДОНТА. ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

LOCAL APPLICATION OF EMDOGAIN FL IN PATIENTS WITH PERIODONTAL DISEASE. LITERATURE REVIEW

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Background: Periodontal disease includes periodontal heath, gingival disease and conditions; periodontitis; other conditions affecting the periodontium; peri-implant disease, and conditions according to the current classification adopted by the EFP & AAP World Workshop in Amsterdam, on Europerio 2017 [1]. Gingivitis and periodontitis are the most common diseases in the adult population. Periodontitis is an inflammatory-dystrophic condition characterized by the formation of periodontal pockets due to the destruction of the periodontal ligament and loss of bone tissue. The search for local drugs that can restore lost tooth structures is promising in the treatment of this nosology. We can single out Emdogain FL, among such local drugs. Emdogain FL includes enamel matrix derivative (EMD), which is a purified fraction of amelogenins [4]. Emdogain FL is used for periodontal regeneration to improve the prognosis of compromised teeth. Enamel matrix proteins build a matrix that is a trigger for the proliferation and differentiation of mesenchymal cells with the formation of new cementum on the surface of tooth roots. This in turn is the basis for the regeneration of periodontal ligaments and alveolar bone. This is how functional attachment regenerates [3]. Emdogain FL consists of two syringes, one of which is PrefGel, which is 24% EDTA, needed to remove the smeared layer from the tooth root surface and is a collagen matrix for dentin surfaces. Another syringe is directly EMD. The drug is used in the first phase of treatment, after a previous SRP [2].

Purpose of work: A systematic review of the literature on the effect of application of Emdogain FL in patients with periodontal disease

Materials and methods: The analysis of literary sources was carried out. Relevant materials were found in the search platforms like PubMed and Google Scholar, using searching by keywords and titles. Ten articles were developed, 5 of which concerned the surgical treatment of periodontitis with Emdogain, 5 of which related to the conservative treatment of chronic periodontitis with Emdogain FL.

Results of a study and Conclusion: Local application of Emdogain FL has a positive effect on periodontal status in patients with periodontal disease, by regeneration of periodontal ligaments and alveolar bone, as evidenced by clinical measurement of periodontal pocket depth and radiological monitoring [2].

Literature:

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3. Zetterstrom et al. 1997
4. Зуккелли Дж. Пластическая хирургия мягких тканей полости рта; с "Азбука", г. Москва, 2014 г. с. 150

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